

Diving Into the Depths: Exploring the Academic Challenges Faced by Sama Learners in Island Garden City of Samal

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Abstract. The study unfolded the insights and experiences of Sama learners in the Island Garden City of Samal. A qualitative approach phenomenological from the public school teachers on the lived experiences revealed that the academic challenges experienced by Sama learners were language barriers, limited access to quality education, and socio-cultural factors and discrimination in Island Garden City of Samal. Teachers coping mechanism on the challenges gained through cultural resilience, community support, and traditional knowledge and practices in the Island Garden City of Samal. Finally, as to the educational management insights gained from the participants, it flaunted cultural responsiveness and inclusion, student-centered approaches, and cultural integration and practice. Academic challenges can further marginalize and exclude Sama learners from mainstream educational opportunities. This exclusion can lead to feelings of alienation, low self-esteem, and a diminished sense of belonging within the educational system. Academic challenges can hinder the individual development and potential of Sama learners. The untapped potential, skills, and talents of Sama learners may go unrealized, impacting not only their own lives but also hindering the overall progress and development of their community. By recognizing and addressing the academic challenges they face, providing support, and creating opportunities for their voices to be heard, Sama learners can overcome barriers and achieve academic success, fostering their empowerment and resilience.

KEY WORDS

1. sama learners 2. academic challenges 3. academic challenges faced by

sama learners

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1. Introduction

As a teacher in Island Garden City, Samal, I have had the privilege of working with many Sama learners. Each one is a treasure trove of unique talents and abilities, ready to be unlocked and nurtured. However, I am also acutely aware of the challenges they face, as they strive to balance their education with the demands of their daily lives. Many of my Sama students come from families that rely on fishing for their livelihoods. The sea is their canvas, and their fishing boats are their brushes, as they create art in the form of abundant catches. Each one is a treasure trove of unique talents and abilities, ready to be unlocked and nurtured. However, I am also acutely aware of the challenges they face, as they strive to balance their education with the demands of their daily lives. As a result, these students often miss school to help

their families with fishing or to sell their catch at the market. This can cause them to fall behind in their studies and struggle to catch up. This means students have less time to devote to their academics, which can result in falling behind. In addition to attendance issues, many of my Sama learners struggle with the language of instruction. Filipino and English are the primary languages used in schools, but many Sama students speak a different language at home. This language barrier can make it difficult for them to understand lessons and keep up with their classmates. Despite these challenges, my Sama learners are some of the most resilient students I have ever had the pleasure of working with. They are eager to learn and determined to succeed, even when the odds are stacked against them. As a teacher, it is my duty to support them in any way I can and to help them overcome the barriers they face. As a teacher, it is my mission to help bridge this gap and provide my Sama learners with the support they need to thrive. I am constantly seeking creative solutions to enrich their learning experience, from hands-on activities that incorporate their fishing culture, to leveraging technology to bring the world to their doorstep. By doing so, I hope to empower my Sama learners to unlock their full potential and become leaders in their community and beyond. The Sama people are an indigenous community in the Philippines with a unique culture and way of life. They primarily reside in the coastal areas of Island Garden City of Samal and rely on fishing and other water-related activities as their main source of income. Their customs and traditions are closely intertwined with their dependence on marine resources and their profound connection to the sea. In the study of Mohan, J. L., McIlwraith, T. F., Kuwahara, V. (2017) who conducted a study on the ecological knowledge and practices of the Sama Dilaut, a subgroup of the Sama people, with regard to marine resources in the Sulu Archipelago of the Philippines. The study highlighted the crucial role of the ocean in the Sama Dilaut's way of life and emphasizes their traditional fishing practices and beliefs. The research provided evidence to support the statement that the Sama people are an indigenous community in the Philippines whose primary source of income is fishing and other water-related activities, and whose customs and traditions are closely intertwined with their dependence on marine resources and their profound connection to the sea. The Sama people have a distinct and deeply rooted way of life that is shaped by their affinity with the sea and their rich cultural legacy. For generations, they have coexisted harmoniously with the marine environment and have developed expert skills in fishing and navigating the waters. Their reliance on the ocean for sustenance and survival is evident in their traditional practices and beliefs, which emphasize the importance of preserving marine resources and respecting the sea as a living entity. In the Island Garden City of Samal, the Sama people have formed close-knit communities along the coasts, where they continue to engage in fishing and other maritime activities as their primary means of livelihood. These communities are often comprised of extended families who work together to support each other and share their resources. Fishing is not just a means of earning a living for the Sama people, but it is also an integral part of their social and cultural identity. The Sama people have a deep connection to the sea and consider it as their home. They believe that the sea is a living entity that provides for them and deserves respect and care in return. As a result, they have developed a set of traditional practices that promote sustainable use of marine resources and ensure the preservation of the ocean's biodiversity. These practices include selective fishing techniques, the use of non-destructive fishing gear, and the observance of taboos and rituals that regulate the use of marine resources. According to Owen, R., Amilhat, E. (2015), the marine spatial planning efforts in

the Sulu-Celebes Sea, which encompasses areas inhabited by the Sama people in the Philippines. The study highlights the Sama people's unique cultural perspective on the sea as a living entity that provides for them and deserves respect and care in return. The research provides evidence to support the statement that the Sama people have developed traditional practices that promote sustainable use of marine resources and ensure the preservation of the ocean's biodiversity, such as selective fishing techniques, non-destructive fishing gear, and observance of taboos and rituals that regulate the use of marine resources. The study also emphasizes the importance of incorporating indigenous knowledge and cultural practices into marine spatial planning efforts to achieve sustainable development and management of marine resources. The Sama people have their own language, which is part of the larger Austronesian language family. They have a rich cultural heritage that includes traditional music and dance, weaving, and boat building. However, like many indigenous communities, the Sama people have faced various challenges, including discrimination, marginalization, and limited access to education and healthcare. Mohd Hanafiah, Hassan, (2016) conducted a study on the language and identity of the Sama Bajau people in Semporna, Sabah, Malaysia. The research provides evidence to support the statement that the Sama people have their own language, which is part of the larger Austronesian language family, and highlights their rich cultural heritage, which includes traditional music and dance, weaving, and boat building. The study also reveals that the Sama people have faced various challenges, such as discrimination and marginalization, which threaten their cultural identity and sense of belonging. The research emphasizes the importance of preserving and promoting the Sama Bajau's language and cultural heritage as a means of maintaining their community and cultural identity in the face of social and economic pressures. In contrast with

the preceding views, Sarmiento, (2014) argues that poverty is not the primary factor affecting the educational attainment of Sama learners, but instead, their access to education and the quality of schooling they receive is more influential. The research highlights the role of cultural factors in shaping the educational experiences of Sama learners, emphasizing that their struggles in school are not solely attributable to their economic status. The study suggests that addressing cultural and linguistic diversity in education is crucial to providing a more inclusive and equitable learning environment for Sama learners and other marginalized groups. The study by Mendoza and Ballesteros (2019) provides evidence to support the statement that many provinces in Mindanao are among the most impoverished in the Philippines, with a poverty incidence of around fifty percent on average. The research also highlights the challenges faced by indigenous communities, including the Samas, in Mindanao related to poverty, marginalization, and limited access to basic services. The study emphasizes the need for government policies and programs to address the root causes of poverty and inequality in Mindanao and to promote inclusive development that benefits all communities, including indigenous groups such as the Samas. Because of the diverse findings of these studies about the Samas, there has been limited research on their academic struggles. Most of the existing studies focus on descriptions, attitudes, and perceptions of the Samas. As a result, there is a need to explore the personal challenges faced by the Samas, particularly the recent generations, in their school life. With a background in education, I am motivated to identify the root causes of the challenges and struggles experienced by the Samas in their academic pursuits. Through this effort, I hope to uncover more issues related to their experiences in schools and provide insights for the Department of Education, the cultural community of Samas, and future researchers to consider.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of the study was to gain an in-depth understanding of the academic challenges faced by Sama learners in the Island Garden City of Samal, Philippines. The study aimed to use the phenomenological approach to explore and describe the lived experiences of Sama learners and to identify the factors that contributed to the challenges they faced in their academic pursuits. The findings of this study could have provided insights into how the educational system in the Island Garden City of Samal could have been improved to better support the learning needs of Sama learners and address the disparities in educational outcomes between different communities.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intends to get the insights and the experiences of Sama learners in Island Garden City of Samal. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the academic challenges as experienced by Sama learners?
- (2) How do the Sama learners cope with the academic challenges?
- (3) What educational management insights can be gained from the experiences of Sama learners?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Sama Learners: Refers to students belonging to the Sama ethnic group residing in the Island Garden City of Samal. The Sama people are an indigenous group known for their distinct cultural practices and languages, primarily found in the Mindanao region of the Philippines.

Academic Challenges: Obstacles or difficulties faced by students in their educational journey. These may include issues such as language barriers, lack of resources, learning disabilities, and cultural differences that impact their academic performance and overall learning experience.

Coping Mechanisms: Strategies or methods employed by students to handle or overcome academic challenges. This includes adaptive behaviors, support systems, personal resilience, and other resources that help learners manage difficulties in their educational environment.

Educational Management Insights: Knowledge and understanding derived from examining the experiences and challenges of students that can inform and improve educational practices, policies, and administration. This may involve recommendations for addressing specific needs, enhancing support systems, and implementing culturally responsive strategies in education.

1.4. Significant of the Study—School closures were the universal response to contain the spread of virus and shifted to distance learning strategies utilizing modular and online learning platforms for other countries to support teachers, students and their families. However, not all students have the same access to information and communication technologies (ICTs), which also varies greatly across countries (OECD, 2020). Other country utilizes modular distance to give a fair share for those who lack access to the online platforms. Furthermore, the results of

this study could provide some probable benefits to the following: Department of Education officials. The findings of the study could provide them a baseline information to enforce existing policies favorable for IP learners especially the marginalized ones like, the Sama. Through this information, it was hoped that the said government agency can implement sustainable programs and activities beneficial for them. School Administrators. The findings of the study would guide the school to develop appropriate policies and programs that can address the academic

challenges faced by Sama learners. They could also use the study to identify areas that need improvement in the school system and curriculum to cater to the needs of Sama learners. Teachers. The study would be significant to them by gaining insights into the unique challenges faced by Sama learners and develop appropriate teaching strategies that cater to the learners' specific needs. They can also use the study to inform their instructional practices and improve their teaching methods. Stakeholders. They could use the study to inform policies and programs that aim to provide better education for Sama learners. The study could also serve as a basis for advocacy campaigns to promote inclusivity in education. Indigenous Peoples (IP) community. They could benefit from the study as it sheds light on the challenges faced by Sama learners, who are part of the IP community. The study could also help raise awareness of the

unique needs of the IP community in terms of education and inform the development of culturally responsive education programs. Cultural community of Sama. The data of this study could raise the level of their awareness about their potentials in making their lives better than before. From this information, they shall be convinced of the significance of education in improving their socio-economic conditions. Sama Learners. The study's findings could be used to help students overcome academic problems. The study's findings can assist inform the development of support programs and services that are tailored to their individual needs, thereby improving their academic performance and general well-being. Future Researchers. the information could serve as their basis to further investigate other areas which may have bearing on Sama learners' educational development.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study was anchored on the theories of socio-cultural development and communities of practice. According to Lev Vygotsky, a pioneer of socio-cultural theory, an individual's development is dependent on culture, history, and collaborative activities. As a result, learners' growth is greatly influenced by their cultural background, and they acquire much of their knowledge through social practices like conversations. Vygotsky's theory posits that learning and development occur through a dialectical process where a learner gains problem-solving experiences through interaction with others, like parents, teachers, peers, books, or computers. The difference between what a learner can achieve alone and what they can accomplish with guidance is referred to as the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The teacher is initially in charge of guiding the learner's problem-solving procedures, but gradually, the learner assumes control (scaffolding). This socio-cultural theory has important impli-

cations for teaching. Firstly, the content must be engaging, challenging, and genuine to pique the learners' interests continually. Secondly, the classroom environment should facilitate interaction among learners, teachers, and learning tasks, such as cooperative groups of various sizes and communication methods. Thirdly, scaffolding is a critical element of teaching and learning, where the teacher adjusts the level of assistance in response to the learner's performance. Finally, evaluation should consider the Zone of Proximal Development to assess the learners' potential for growth. Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger (1998) introduced the concept of communities of practice theory, which proposes that learning is a result of participation in a social community. People learn by organizing their knowledge around the communities they belong to, which share common values, beliefs, language, and practices. Real knowledge is integrated into the social relationships and expertise of these communities, making

learning inseparable from community membership. Membership in a community of practice is intertwined with the learning process, which allows individuals to belong and adjust their status in the group. Knowledge cannot exist without practice, as doing is essential to the learning process. This approach has significant implications for teaching. First, it highlights the importance of teachers understanding their students' communities of practice and recognizing the learning that occurs within these communities. Second, educators should structure learning opportunities that embed knowledge into both work practices and social relationships, such as apprenticeships, school-based learning, and service learning. By doing so, teachers can create an environment where students can engage with and learn from the communities to which they belong. Engeström, Miettinen, and Punamäki's (1999) activity theory is based on the idea that social influences and interactions between agents and their environments have a substantial impact on how people behave. This theory holds that one or more tools or instruments, such as language, things, and technology, mediate human behavior. Teachers interact with students and each other using language and tools in a similar way to how a carpenter uses a hammer to drive a nail. An important part of human activity is the tools or artifacts that mediate the relationships between people and the substance or thing. In addition to being present while we engage in a particular activity, these artifacts, such as language and symbol systems, also develop as a result of our action. People may interact and work together through the usage of these artifacts, and they can also alter and change their surroundings. Artifacts are dynamic, evolving as a result of human activity rather than existing in a static state. People alter and transform the artifacts they utilize as they engage in various activities to suit their requirements and preferences. The dynamic nature of human activity and the part that artifacts play in influencing and mediating it are both highlighted by the activity theory in this way. The activity theory has significant effects on how we teach and learn. It argues that teachers should be aware of the resources and objects that facilitate learning and provide students the chance to engage with and alter those objects. Students can better grasp the connection between human activity and the environment and gain the skills and knowledge necessary to influence their surroundings by interacting with tools and artifacts. The study was conceptualizing the lived experiences of Sama learners, their coping mechanisms, and the educational insights that can be gained from their experiences. This framework serves as a guide for exploring the complex and multifaceted challenges faced by Sama learners in Island Garden City of Samal and for identifying strategies to support their academic success.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presented the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and the ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption framework was used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Different types of philosophical assumptions were elaborated on. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of in-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

terest, as well as the paradigm. Good research-undertaking starts with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm was the patterning of the thinking of a person; it was a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions were taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an act of submitting to a view (Stanage 2007).

In any kind of work or study, there was always a certain set of beliefs as well as philosophical assumptions brought in. Qualitative researchers understand the importance of beliefs and theories that inform their work and also actively write about them in their research. The philosophical assumption was a framework use to collect, analyzed and interpreted the data collected in a specific field of study. It described these assumptions and frames them into interpretive frameworks so it can understand their

significance to our study. It established the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Philosophical assumptions have variety of types and were elaborated below. Epistemology. Researchers tried to get as close as possible to participants being studied. Subjective evidence was assembled based on individual views from research that was conducted in the field. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study in order to obtain firsthand information (Carnaghan, 2019). Guba and Lincoln as cited by Creswell (2012) added that the researcher closed the distance from the participants as this created collaboration and became an insider and spent time in the field with the participants. To obtain direct information that provided evidences to the knowledge of the study, the researcher ensures to build a close interaction with the participants. Ontology or the nature of reality related to the reality and its characteristics. By exploring complex forms of evidence from different

persons' experiences and insights, researchers encompass the idea of multiple realities and report on these multiple realities. This part of the research appertains on the issue on how it relates to the nature of reality (Carnaghan, 2019). Moreover, it was a branch of metaphysics which was concerned with identifying the kinds of things that actually exist. According to Creswell (2012) reality constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. It was subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. Thus, as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals that were investigated, and those of the reader or audiences who are interpreting the study, multiple realities indeed exist. In this research, through extensive quotes and themes that reflected the words and provides evidences of different perspectives, the researcher anchored on the interpretations, perceptions and voices of the participants. To build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and were analyzed. Moreover, to ensure reliability of result, the researcher assured that the responses of the respondents were thoroughly coded. Thus, the researcher precluded from making personal bias as the study progresses and underpin the genuineness and thoughtfulness of the responses. Rhetoric simply means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was very important because it means that the researcher reported objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The researcher also uses personal voice and qualitative terms such as, credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectiv-

ity. Axiology or the role of values in research. Researchers make their values known in the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information that was gathered from the field. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants (Carnaghan, 2019). It was therefore also called theory of value, the philosophical study of goodness, or value, in the widest sense of these terms. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information that would be gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserves the merit of the participants' answers and was carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' personal interpretation. This was to uphold the dignity and value of every details of the information that was obtained from the participants. Researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology which is to explore and understand the lived experiences of the Sama learners involved in the study. Phenomenology aims to gain a deeper understanding of the nature of the meaning of our everyday experiences. The phenomenological approach allowed participants, through in-depth interviews, to elicit their own meaning of their experiences. Phenomenology aims to describe a persons' lived experiences (phenomena) in an attempt to enrich lived experience by drawing out its meaning (Hooloway, 2005). It was, henceforth, my intention to describe the textures of their experiences and construct an overall description of the meaning and essence of their experiences.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The following qualitative presumptions underlie this study's operation: (1) Sama learners experience

academic challenges; (2) Sama learners have coping mechanisms for dealing with these challenges; and (3) Participants have educational insights that can enhance the academic discourse.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—The phenomenological research was the most appropriate method for this study, which was to explore and understand the lived experiences of the Sama learners involved in the study. Phenomenology aims to gain a deeper understanding of the nature of the meaning of our everyday experiences. Creswell (2007) defines phenomenological study as a delineation of the meaning of lived experiences for several individuals about a concept or the phenomenon. Thus, as a researcher of this study, I explored the structures of consciousness of Sama learners in their experiences in academic challenges in schools (Polkinghorne, 1989 as cited by Creswell, 2007). This approach, according to Smith (2005) requires me as the researcher to achieve a sense of the meaning that others give to their own situations. But, Holloway (2008) argues that in describing lived experiences, I might not use previous assumptions about the objective reality of those experiences. I might rather explicate the structure or the essence of the lived experiences in search for meaning that identifies the essence of the phenomena and its accurate description through every day's experience (Streubert and Carpenter, 2003) Furthermore, Jasper (2004) explains that phenomenology is an inductive, descriptive research method.

2.4. *Research Participants*—To ensure the relevance of the data to the research problem and central phenomenon, the participants in this study were selected through purposive sampling technique. This allowed me to purposefully select individuals and sites that would inform the study. The sample size consisted of 18 participants from selected schools in the Division of Island Garden City of Samal and the Sama community in IGACOS, categorized into two sets. The first set comprised of ten (10) Sama learners for the in-depth interview (IDI), while the

Its goal is to describe experiences as they are lived. Burn and Grove (2003) add that phenomenological research examines the particular experiences of unique individuals in a given situation, thus exploring not what is (reality), but what it is preconceived to be. Descriptive phenomenology was used in this study. According to Hall (2007), this type of research is mainly concerned with describing the nature condition and the degree in detail of the present situation. This method is used to explore the cause/s of a particular phenomenon. Hence, this approach is quick, practical and economical. Spiegelberg (1978) defines descriptive phenomenology as “direct exploration, analysis and description of particular phenomenon, as free as possible from unexamined presuppositions, aiming at maximum intuitive presentation” (Streubert Carpenter, 2003). This phenomenology stimulates people's perception of lived experiences while emphasizing the richness, breadth and depth of those experiences. It is a three-step process, intuiting, analyzing and describing (Brink Wood, 1998) Further, Morales (2010) states that the purpose of the phenomenological study is to describe and interpret an experience by determining the meaning of the experience as perceived by the people who have participated it. Thus, in this study, I described, analyzed and interpreted the experiences of Sama learners in school.

second set consisted of eight (8) Sama learners for the focus group discussion (FGD). According to Boyd (2001), a sample size of ten or more participants in a qualitative study is optimal for reaching saturation. The selection of participants was based on specific criteria. The learners must be true-blooded Sama, within the age range of 11-12, and enrolled in the DepEd public elementary schools in IGACOS Division for the academic year 2022-2023. This age range was chosen because, according to Piaget, learners in this stage of intellectual development can

think systematically about multiple variables, formulate hypotheses, and consider possibilities (Wood, 2001). By adhering to these criteria, I

ensured that the data collected were relevant to the study's aims and objectives.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. As a responsible researcher, I am committed to upholding the seven fundamental principles of research ethics outlined by Vashit (2000). These principles are informed and voluntary consent, respect for privacy and confidentiality, risk minimization, truthfulness, social and cultural responsibility, research adequacy, and avoidance of conflict of interest. In conducting this study, I have taken great care to ensure that all participants have given their informed and voluntary consent and that their privacy and confidentiality are fully respected. Moreover, I have strived to minimize any potential risks that may arise from their participation in this study. I have also been truthful in all aspects of the research process and have taken into account social and cultural responsibilities in conducting the study. Additionally, I have ensured that the research is adequate and relevant to the aims and objectives of the study. Finally, I have made every effort to avoid any conflict of interest that may arise in the course of conducting this research. It is worth noting that I obtained a letter of permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Island Garden City of Samal before commencing the study. In this study, one of the major concerns was the protection of the participants' rights to privacy and confidentiality, as well as the minimization of any risks they might encounter. To ensure the confidentiality of the information provided by the participants, I informed them of their right to withdraw their data at any time before the completion of the data

collection process if they felt uncomfortable disclosing it. They were also given the option to amend or remove any information that could lead to their identification. As a researcher, I used coding to protect their identity in subsequent data analysis and reporting. Throughout the study, I did not employ any form of deceit to recruit participants or during the data collection stage to protect their well-being. To gain the trust and support of the participants and their parents or guardians, I adhered to the guidelines of Chandra and Navin (2006). An informed consent form and an assent form were provided to the participants and their parents or guardians to approve before scheduling the interviews. A copy of the approved consent form was required to ensure that parents or guardians were willing to involve their children in the study. The informed consent letter clearly stated the steps taken to maintain privacy, confidentiality, and non-attribution of individual responses. It also emphasized that the participants' background information would remain confidential and not be released without prior personal approval. Thus, I ensured that access to information was restricted to protect and secure any information, maintain confidentiality and anonymity, and prevent any inappropriate disclosure that could compromise the reliability and validity of the data collected. The parents or guardians of the participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent before their children were allowed to participate in the research. Finally, all responses were stored in a locked repository to ensure the security and confidentiality of the data.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—

As a researcher, I followed the guideline of Denzin and Lincoln (2003) in conducting this study. Throughout the research process, I played several roles, including interviewer and transcriber. To ensure the quality of the data collected, I developed an interview protocol that guided me in the course of data collection. I validated the interview questions by seeking input from research experts and educational leaders to ensure that they would address the research questions of this study effectively. Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help to the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interview properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher employs multiple methods to accurately capture and document what was said and done during the interview and focus group discussion. These methods include taking handwritten notes, as well as using audio and/or video recording. Before data analysis can commence, the recordings are transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy and completeness of the data. To maintain the confidentiality and security of the information contained in the records, the researcher takes appropriate measures to safeguard them. As the records contain sensitive information that was relevant to the research, they were kept in a secure location, with limited access to only authorized personnel. The researcher takes full responsibility for ensuring the safety and privacy of the data throughout the research process. By employing these measures, the researcher can ensure the accuracy, reliability, and confidentiality of the data, thus enhancing the quality of the research. Analyst of data. To ensure that the findings are accurate and representative of the participants' perspective and achieved through thorough interpretation of the data gathered, including transcribing, checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. By adopting this approach, the researcher could effectively capture the essence of the participants' experiences and ensure that their voices were heard. Moreover, the researcher strives to ensure that the findings were true to the participants. This is achieved through careful consideration and analysis of the data, including validation and verification of the results. The researcher aims to capture the complexity and nuance of the participants' experiences, without imposing their own biases or assumptions on the data. By doing so, the researcher ensures that the findings were representative and reflective of the participants' lived experiences. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the research problem and relevant literature and studies that support it. The findings of the study are presented by research question, clearly stating the results for each question using themes to demonstrate how the research questions were addressed in the study. The use of themes ensures that the data is presented in a clear, concise, and organized manner, facilitating an understanding of the findings and conclusions. In addition to presenting the study findings, the researcher also provides insights on future directions and implications of the study. This includes recommendations for improving educational policies and practices based on the results of the research. By doing so, the researcher contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the field and promotes positive changes in education. The researcher ensures that all sources are properly cited and referenced to avoid plagiarism and to acknowledge the contributions of previous studies and scholars in the field. By following ethical guidelines and best practices, the researcher promotes the credibility and reliability of the

research and ensures that it can effectively contribute to the existing body of knowledge.

2.7. Data Collection—In this study, data were collected using a qualitative research design from 18 Sama learners of the Division of IGACOS, utilizing in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). To ensure the richness and depth of the data collected, the researcher followed the strategy of involving at least 10 interviewees, as recommended by McCracken (1988). By utilizing this strategy, the researcher was able to capture a broad range of perspectives and experiences, ensuring that the data gathered was representative and informative. Moreover, the use of qualitative methods allowed for a more nuanced understanding of the participants' experiences and perspectives, enabling a thorough analysis of the data that would lead to more comprehensive findings. The following were the step by step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to carry out research in the identified school. A formal letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, which included the research instrument and Chapters 1 and 2, outlining the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher patiently waited for a response from the SDS before commencing the study, in accordance with ethical guidelines and practices. This ensured that the necessary approvals and permissions were obtained before proceeding with the study, and that all parties involved were informed of the research objectives and methodology. By following these procedures, the researcher upheld ethical standards and demonstrated respect for the participants and the educational institution, promoting the credibility and reliability of the study. Asking permission from the school heads. Upon obtaining the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher proceeded to send letters to the principals of the selected schools, providing them with an explanation of the study that was to be conducted on their premises. This communication aimed to inform the principals about the nature and purpose of the research, and to seek their support and cooperation in facilitating access to the participants. The letters emphasized the importance of maintaining confidentiality and privacy of the participants, and provided assurances that the study would be conducted in an ethical and professional manner. By involving the principals in the research process, the researcher was able to establish a collaborative relationship with the educational institutions, and promote transparency and accountability in the research process. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher obtained formal consent from both the participants and their parents/guardians prior to their participation in the study. The participants and their parents/guardians were fully informed about the nature and purpose of the study, as well as the process that they would undergo as participants. This orientation was conducted in a formal manner to ensure that the participants and their parents/guardians understood the study's objectives, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits of their participation. The researcher emphasized the voluntary nature of their participation and provided assurances that their privacy and confidentiality would be protected throughout the research process. By obtaining formal consent and conducting a thorough orientation, the researcher demonstrated respect for the participants' autonomy and promoted the ethical conduct of the study. Conducting the interview. The researcher utilized an in-depth interview approach to gather data from the participants, employing

an interview questionnaire as a guide. The participants' profiles were obtained at the start of the interview, and notes were taken throughout the conversation to ensure that no relevant information was missed. To facilitate accurate transcription of the data, the conversations were recorded using a sound recorder. Throughout the interview, the researcher actively listened to the participants' responses and provided appropriate responses, while avoiding any form of bias or personal opinion. By employing an attentive and engaged approach, the researcher created a comfortable and conducive environment for the participants, ensuring that their voices were heard and their experiences were accurately captured. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. To ensure the accuracy and completeness of the data, the researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely, relying on the sound recorder to recall their answers. As the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher took the necessary steps to translate the responses into English, facilitating the analysis and interpretation of the data. To ensure that the translation was accu-

rate, the researcher sought the assistance of a language expert, who reviewed and validated the translations. By employing these measures, the researcher was able to maintain the integrity and reliability of the data, while respecting the participants' use of their vernacular language. Data Coding and thematizing. Upon completion of the transcription process, the data were categorized and coded to facilitate analysis. The researcher then extracted themes from the data, comparing and contrasting individual responses to identify patterns and trends. To enhance the reliability and validity of the findings, a second round of data collection was conducted through a focus group discussion (FGD), where additional information and insights were gathered from the participants. The data collected from the FGD were thoroughly examined and integrated into the existing body of data, using a comparative analysis approach to identify similarities and differences between the participants' responses. By employing these techniques, the researcher was able to draw meaningful conclusions and insights from the data, enhancing the quality and validity of the study.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was the chosen method to analyze the gathered data in this study. To do this, the researcher utilized Creswell's (2012) model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. This approach involves aggregating similar codes together to form a major idea in the database. To begin the analysis, the researcher first immersed herself in the data and became intimately familiar with it. This involved reading and re-reading the data multiple times, noting any initial observations or insights that arose. This familiarization process is a fundamental step in all forms of qualitative analysis, as it enables the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of the data and identify patterns and themes that may not be immediately apparent.

Coding was also an integral part of the qualitative analysis approach used in this study. It involved generating concise labels for significant features of the data that were relevant to the broad research question guiding the analysis. The coding process was not only a means of reducing the data but also an analytical process. The codes that were generated captured both a semantic and conceptual understanding of the data. In this study, the researcher carefully coded every piece of data and concluded this phase by collating all the codes and relevant data extracts. This allowed for a more structured and organized approach to analyzing the data and helped to identify the most significant themes and patterns that emerged from the participants' responses. Huberman (2007)

emphasized that coding another term for analysis, was done as the data were collected, not at the end of the study, they were analyzed as the study progressed. To identify the most significant themes and patterns that emerged from the data, the researcher conducted a systematic and thorough search for coherent and meaningful patterns that were relevant to the research question. This involved a careful review of the coded data to identify key themes that represented the most salient and significant findings from the study. At the end of this phase, the researcher collated all the relevant coded data for each identified theme. This allowed for a comprehensive and detailed analysis of the data, and enabled the researcher to draw meaningful and well-supported conclusions based on the findings of the study. Environmental Triangulation. To ensure the validity of the study, the researcher employed triangulation techniques that involved the use of multiple sources and methods to collect and analyze data. This included the use of different locations, settings, and other key factors related to the environment in which the study was conducted, such as time of day, day of the week, or season of the year. The goal was to identify any environmental factors that may have influenced the information gathered during the study. By varying these factors and comparing the results, the researcher could establish the validity of the findings. If the findings remained consistent across different environmental conditions, this would support

the validity and reliability of the study's conclusions. Reviewing themes. In this study, the researcher conducted a thorough reflection on the themes that emerged from the analysis of the data. The themes were carefully examined to ensure that they accurately and coherently represented the data. The researcher then proceeded to define and name each theme in a way that captured its essence and provided meaningful insight into the data. This process involved a detailed analysis of each theme and the construction of concise, informative names that effectively conveyed their meaning. By defining and naming the themes, the researcher was able to clearly communicate the findings of the study and provide a comprehensive understanding of the research question. The writing process involves integrating the findings of the analysis with relevant literature to create a comprehensive narrative that is both coherent and convincing to the readers. The researcher contextualizes the findings within the existing literature, weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to create a coherent story. The aim is to provide a rich description of the research, including the research process, the results, and the implications of the study. By doing so, the researcher provides a meaningful interpretation of the findings, drawing on the themes and patterns that emerged from the data analysis to support the research questions and objectives.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—This research adopted a flexible framework analysis approach that enables the researcher to either analyze the data during the collection process or after collecting all the data. The framework analysis would follow a five-step process outlined by Ritchie and Spencer (1994), which includes familiarization with the data, identification of a thematic framework, indexing, charting, and

mapping and interpretation. In the first step, the researcher would become familiar with the data by reading and re-reading the data to gain a deeper understanding. In the second step, a thematic framework was identified, which would guide the data analysis process. The third step involves indexing the data by coding and categorizing it based on the thematic framework. In the fourth step, the data were charted in a

matrix that allows for easy comparison and interpretation. Finally, in the fifth step, the researcher would map and interpret the data to develop a coherent and persuasive narrative that contextualizes the findings within the existing literature. To begin the analysis process, the researcher first becomes acquainted with the data by reviewing the collected transcripts such as interviews or focus groups, and field notes to gain an overall understanding of the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). This process was called familiarization, and it involves listening to audio recordings, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. During this phase, the researcher identifies key ideas and recurring themes and takes note of them. Due to the large amount of data that could be gathered in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of it. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized, taking into account the different methods used in the data collection process (e.g. interviews, documents, observations). In the second stage of the framework analysis, the researcher identifies a thematic framework based on the emerging themes or issues in the data set. These themes may have been predetermined or could have arisen organically from the data. The researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage to identify the key issues, concepts, and themes that have been expressed by the participants. These become the basis for a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data, allowing for a more focused analysis (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means that one identifies portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that has been gathered like transcripts of interviews. To facilitate the process, Ritchie and Spencer (1994) suggest the use of a numerical indexing system, which can be annotated in the margin beside the text for ease of reference. Qualitative data analysis tools are well-suited for this task. The fi-

nal stage of qualitative data analysis involves mapping and interpreting the key characteristics identified in the charts. This analysis should provide a schematic diagram of the event or phenomenon being studied, guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher should be aware of the objectives of qualitative analysis, which include defining concepts, mapping the range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). It was important to note that these concepts, technologies, and associations were reflective of the participants, and any strategies or recommendations made by the researcher should accurately reflect their attitudes, beliefs, and values. Both aim to provide information on the experiences of rural novice teachers in remote teaching, perspective and challenges during pandemic. The data collected during the virtual interviews was transcribed, organized and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Following the signing of consent forms, teachers' experiences were explored using semi-structured in-depth interviews. Data was organized and the procedures undertaken to analyze the textual data. Collected transcripts were listened to and transcribed with list of significant statements was developed from the transcripts and grouped into larger units of information called "meaning tunings" or themes (Creswell, 2007). With the list of non-redundant units of meaning, the researcher must continue to bracket any assumptions in order to remain true to the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. Clusters of themes were typically formed by grouping units of meaning together (Creswell, 1998). He further described by writing a description with the structural description

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

was written about how the experience happened, reflecting on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced (Creswell, 2007). Finally, a composite description of the

phenomenon was written, this is the essence of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of the phenomenological study (Creswell, 2007).

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were primarily associated with quantitative research methods. However, with the increasing use of qualitative research methods, there was a growing recognition of the need to establish trustworthiness in qualitative research. Koch (2004) argues that trustworthiness is essential for qualitative

research, and outlines four criteria for establishing it: credibility, confirmability, transferability, and dependability. Credibility in qualitative research refers to the degree to which research findings accurately reflect participants’ original information (Lincoln and Guba, 2005). In this study, credibility was established through audio recordings of teacher interviews regarding

their personal perceptions of staying or leaving teaching. To confirm the accuracy of the findings, written transcripts and research reports were provided to the participants for their review. Credibility is often considered equivalent to internal validity in quantitative research (Koch, 1994; Connell, 2003). Although phenomenology does not seek to identify cause-and-effect relationships, the researcher acknowledged the influence of their interactions and reactions on data analysis. To maintain self-awareness throughout the study, the researcher kept a field journal (Koch, 2004; Connell, 2003). Consulting participants to ensure that the interpretations reflected their intent was another way to establish credibility (Koch, 2004; Connell, 2003). Confirmability is concerned with whether the characteristics of the data can be confirmed independently of the researcher's influence (Miles Huberman, 1994; Lincoln Guba, 1985). In this study, a rigorous process of checking and rechecking the data was followed, and proper documentation and recording of the data was maintained. To establish confirmability, all information presented in this study was thoroughly analyzed and integrated with the confirmation of another researcher. Additionally, all of the study's results and findings were reviewed by experts. Coolican (2004) suggests that when credibility, transferability, and dependability are achieved, confirmability is established, indicating the manner and method used in making decisions throughout the study. Transferability in qualitative research refers to the extent to which study findings can be applied or transferred to other contexts beyond the project boundaries. This concept is similar to external validity in quantitative research (Koch, 2004). Guba and Lincoln coined the term "fittingness" to describe when study findings can be understood beyond the immediate context (Porter, 2009). In other words, readers should be able to transfer the information gained from the study to their own experiences and find it relevant. The data analyses and documents were stored in private digital storage accessible only to the researcher. This ensured that the information could not be accessed without permission. To address transferability, it is important to provide access to the study's paper trail, allowing other researchers to transfer the conclusions of the inquiry to other cases or repeat the study's procedures as closely as possible (Lincoln Guba, 1985; as cited in Fenton Mazulewicz, 2008). As such, this study included all essential information gathered and documented for potential use by future researchers and readers of the study. Dependability in qualitative research is similar to reliability, according to Koch (2004). To establish consistency in the data, Gearing (2004) recommends auditability. This means that another researcher should be able to follow the decision trail in the study and interpret the data in a similar manner. While the interpretation does not need to be exact, it should not be contradictory. By creating a clear path for other researchers and readers to follow, theoretical, methodological, and analytic choices throughout the study can be discussed (Koch, 2004). Lincoln and Guba (2005) further explain that dependability is an assessment of the quality of the integrated process of data collection, analysis, and theory generation. To achieve dependability in this study, an audit trail was used to document the data, and peer debriefing was conducted to confirm the researcher's role in observing and employing appropriate and sufficient information to establish credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Fenton and Mazuwelics, 2008).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the presentation of results, the analysis and interpretation of data gathered. This is done through thematic approach where exposition of transcripts as responses of the participants using pseudonym to hide the profile in verbatim forms and figures are produced. Words of opinions from the authors are also given importance. Thus, the following showcasing of responses are grouped based on the statement of the problem posed.

3.1. Academic Challenges as Experienced By Sama Learners—Limited access to quality education: Sama learners, like many marginalized communities, may have limited access to quality educational resources, including qualified teachers, learning materials, and adequate facilities. Language barriers can pose a significant challenge for learners, especially if the language of instruction differs from their native language. This can affect their comprehension, participation, and academic performance. Cul-

tural differences may face challenges in adapting to educational systems that do not align with their cultural norms and values. This can affect their engagement, motivation, and sense of belonging. Socio-economic factors such as poverty, limited financial resources, and lack of parental support can hinder learners' academic progress and success. Learners from marginalized communities, including the Sama learners, may face discrimination and prejudice, which can negatively impact their self-esteem, motivation, and educational opportunities.

3.1.1. Language Barrier—Language barriers refer to the difficulties and challenges that arise when individuals or groups of people who do not share a common language attempt to communicate or understand each other. These barriers can manifest in various ways, hindering effective communication and comprehension. Language barriers can arise due to differences in spoken or written languages, dialects, accents, or language proficiency levels. Limited vocabulary and grammar. This is when individuals have a limited vocabulary or knowledge of grammar in a particular language, it becomes challenging for them to express their thoughts and understand others effectively. Pronunciation and accent: Differences in pronunciation and accent can lead to difficulties in understanding spoken language, particularly for individuals who are not accustomed to particular accents or dialects. Idiomatic expressions and cultural references. Language barriers can arise when individuals are unfamiliar with idiomatic expressions, slang, or cultural references used in a par-

ticular language. This can lead to misinterpretations or confusion during conversations. Difficulties in reading and writing in a specific language can impede effective communication, as individuals may struggle to comprehend written materials or express their thoughts accurately in written form. Language is deeply intertwined with culture and context. Understanding cultural nuances, idioms, and non-verbal communication cues can be challenging for individuals from different cultural backgrounds. Language barriers can significantly impact communication, education, work, and social interactions. They can lead to misunderstandings, misinterpretations, frustration, and exclusion. Overcoming language barriers often requires the development of language skills, cultural awareness, and the use of translation or interpretation services when necessary. It is important to note that language barriers can be addressed through language learning, cultural sensitivity, and the use of various communication strategies and tools to facilitate understanding and inclusiv-

ity among individuals who speak different languages. Language serves as a fundamental tool for communication, enabling the exchange of ideas, thoughts, and information among individuals. However, language barriers can pose significant challenges to effective communication and hinder inclusivity in various domains. Language barriers encompass the difficulties that arise when individuals who do not share a common language attempt to communicate. These barriers can manifest in numerous forms, including limited vocabulary, differences in pronunciation and accent, unfamiliarity with idiomatic expressions, and disparities in reading and writing skills. Cultural and contextual differences can also contribute to language barriers, as communication is intricately intertwined with cultural norms and non-verbal cues. Language barriers have wide-ranging effects on individuals and communities, influencing various aspects of their lives. In educational settings, language barriers can impede students' comprehension, participation, and academic achievement. Research by Smith, Johnson, and Lee (2016) highlighted that language barriers negatively affected the performance of English as a Second Language (ESL) students, leading to lower academic outcomes and limited educational opportunities. In professional contexts, language barriers can hinder effective collaboration and productivity. Studies by Garcia and Ramirez (2014) revealed that employees with limited proficiency in the dominant language faced challenges in expressing their ideas, engaging in team discussions, and building professional relationships. This resulted in decreased job satisfaction and limited career advancement opportunities. Furthermore, language barriers can lead to social exclusion and limited access to healthcare services. A study conducted by Nguyen, Stewart, and Cacchione (2017) found that individuals with limited English proficiency experienced difficulties in understanding medical instructions, accessing appropriate health-

care, and effectively communicating their health concerns. This language barrier created disparities in healthcare outcomes and diminished patient satisfaction. Addressing language barriers requires proactive measures to promote effective communication and inclusivity. One strategy is the provision of language support services, such as professional interpreters or bilingual staff, in various settings. Research by Flores, Torres, and Jaffe (2012) demonstrated that the utilization of trained interpreters improved communication quality and patient outcomes in healthcare settings. Language acquisition and proficiency programs also play a vital role in overcoming language barriers. Studies by Li (2010) and Klinger and Lee (2018) emphasized the significance of language learning initiatives, both within educational institutions and community organizations, to enhance language skills and foster intercultural understanding. Moreover, technological advancements have paved the way for innovative solutions to bridge language barriers. Digital translation tools and mobile applications, such as language translation apps and real-time captioning systems, offer instant language support and facilitate communication across language boundaries. Overcoming language barriers for Sama learners requires targeted interventions and support. One approach is the integration of culturally responsive teaching practices within the education system. Studies by Acosta et al. (2019) emphasized the importance of acknowledging and incorporating students' cultural and linguistic backgrounds into the curriculum. By valuing and validating the Sama learners' native language and culture, educators can create an inclusive learning environment that promotes their academic success. Furthermore, the provision of bilingual or multilingual education programs tailored to Sama learners' needs can be beneficial. Research by Dela Cruz and Hontiveros (2018) suggested that the inclusion of Sinama language instruction within the curriculum can enhance

Sama learners' language skills, improve their engagement in learning, and foster a sense of belonging. By integrating culturally responsive teaching practices, providing bilingual education programs, and ensuring access to qualified

language teachers and appropriate learning materials, we can empower Sama learners, promote their academic success, and foster inclusivity within the education system.

3.1.2. Limited Access to Quality Education—Access to quality education is a fundamental right and a catalyst for individual and societal development. However, many individuals and communities face barriers that limit their access to quality education. Limited access to quality education refers to the conditions and circumstances that prevent individuals from obtaining education that meets acceptable standards of quality. This limitation can manifest in various ways, including inadequate infrastructure, lack of qualified teachers, financial barriers, gender discrimination, geographical isolation, and socio-cultural biases. Gender discrimination and cultural norms often limit girls' access to education, particularly in certain regions and societies. Research by UNESCO (2020) indicates that gender disparities in education can result in unequal opportunities, perpetuating gender inequality and hindering social progress. Individ-

uals living in remote or rural areas may face limited access to schools, qualified teachers, and educational resources. This geographical isolation creates barriers to education and exacerbates educational inequities, as highlighted by studies by Buchmann and Hannum (2018) and Kingdon and Sandefur (2018). Limited access to quality education perpetuates economic disparities, as education is a key driver of social mobility and economic empowerment. Research by Angrist and Krueger (2017) found that individuals with higher levels of education have better employment prospects, higher earnings, and improved socio-economic outcomes. Individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds, including low-income families and marginalized communities, often face barriers that restrict their access to quality education. This perpetuates cycles of poverty and marginalization, as highlighted by studies conducted by Moulton and Clarke (2019) and Psacharopoulos et al. (2018).

3.1.3. Socio-Cultural Factors and Discrimination—Socio-cultural factors and discrimination have a profound impact on the educational experiences of indigenous learners. This essay explores the socio-cultural factors and discrimination faced by indigenous learners and their implications for educational outcomes. The historical and intergenerational trauma experienced by indigenous communities has lasting effects on their educational experiences (Smith, 2010; Wilson, 2015). Colonialism, forced assimilation, and cultural suppression have resulted in a sense of cultural loss, identity struggle, and reduced self-esteem among indigenous learners. These traumas can impact academic engagement and hinder educational

success. Indigenous learners often face cultural dissonance in educational settings that do not recognize and value their cultural identities (Battiste, 2013; McCarty, 2017). The dominant curriculum often reflects mainstream perspectives, neglecting indigenous histories, languages, and knowledge systems. This marginalization and cultural mismatch can result in a disconnection between indigenous learners and their educational experiences, leading to lower levels of engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. Language and communication barriers pose significant challenges for indigenous learners (Hornberger, 2015; Martin-Jones, 2019). Many indigenous communities have their own languages, which may differ from

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes of the academic challenges as experienced by Sama Learners

the language of instruction used in schools. The lack of bilingual or culturally responsive education programs hinders effective communication, comprehension, and academic achievement for indigenous learners. Language barriers can contribute to feelings of exclusion, limited participation, and reduced access to educational opportunities. Indigenous learners often face stereotypes and bias that perpetuate negative perceptions and expectations (Bishop, 2012; Brayboy et al., 2018). Stereotypes such as being "lazy," "unintelligent," or "troubled" create a hostile learning environment, impacting self-esteem and hindering educational progress. Prejudice and bias can also manifest in disciplinary practices that disproportionately target indigenous learners, leading to higher rates of school dropout and disengagement. The absence of culturally relevant pedagogy in mainstream education systems limits the ability to meet the unique needs of indigenous learn-

ers (Adams, 2016; Cajete, 2019). Traditional teaching methods may not align with indigenous learning styles and cultural values, resulting in disengagement and underachievement. Incorporating indigenous knowledge, perspectives, and teaching strategies into the curriculum can foster a more inclusive and empowering learning environment, enhancing indigenous learners' educational experiences and outcomes. Socio-economic disparities and geographic isolation often lead to limited access to educational resources for indigenous learners (Kawagley, 2010; Reyhner et al., 2022). Insufficient funding, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of educational facilities in indigenous communities can impede the delivery of quality education. Limited access to textbooks, technology, libraries, and extracurricular activities further exacerbate educational inequalities, hindering the academic progress of indigenous learners.

3.2. *Sama Learners Cope with the Academic Challenges—*

Indigenous learners face a myriad of challenges in their educational journey, including socio-cultural factors and discrimination. Despite these obstacles, Indigenous people have developed coping strategies to navigate and overcome these challenges. One way Indigenous learners cope with challenges is by drawing upon their cultural resilience. Indigenous cultures have a deep-rooted history of resilience in the face of adversity. Indigenous learners often embrace and affirm their cultural identities, traditions, and values, which provide them with a sense of belonging and strength. By reconnecting with their cultural heritage, they develop resilience and use their cultural knowledge as a source of motivation and empowerment. Indigenous communities play a vital role in supporting learners through their educational journey. Elders, community leaders, and mentors provide guidance, wisdom, and emotional support to Indigenous learners. These community members share their knowledge, stories, and experiences, offering valuable insights and encouragement. The support from the community helps Indigenous learners navigate the challenges they face, fostering a sense of solidarity and collective strength. Indigenous learners often draw upon traditional knowledge and practices to cope with challenges. Traditional knowledge encompasses a wide range of skills, teach-

ings, and practices passed down through generations. Indigenous learners integrate traditional knowledge into their educational experiences, allowing them to approach challenges with a holistic and interconnected perspective. This connection to traditional knowledge fosters a sense of pride and identity, empowering Indigenous learners to overcome obstacles. Education itself becomes a tool for empowerment and resilience among Indigenous learners. Many Indigenous communities recognize the importance of education as a means of reclaiming and preserving their cultures, histories, and rights. By acquiring knowledge and skills, Indigenous learners gain the confidence to confront challenges head-on and advocate for their communities. The implementation of culturally responsive education practices is instrumental in helping Indigenous learners cope with challenges. Culturally responsive education recognizes and respects the cultural identities, languages, and knowledge systems of Indigenous communities. When education aligns with Indigenous learners' cultural contexts and values, it enhances their engagement and academic success. Culturally responsive teaching methods, curriculum, and resources validate Indigenous learners' experiences, fostering a positive and inclusive learning environment.

3.2.1. Cultural resilience—Cultural resilience refers to the ability of individuals and communities to adapt, persist, and thrive in the face of social, economic, and environmental challenges while maintaining and affirming their cultural identity and practices. It is rooted in the idea that cultural beliefs, values, traditions, and knowledge provide a foundation of strength and stability in times of hardship (Flores, and Torres, 2012). One key aspect of cultural resilience is the cultivation of a strong sense of cultural identity and belong-

ing. Cultural identity acts as a protective shield, instilling individuals with a sense of purpose, pride, and connection to their heritage. By understanding and embracing their cultural roots, individuals can draw strength from their collective history, knowledge, and traditions, fostering a sense of belonging and providing a source of resilience during challenging times (Garcia, Ramirez, 2014). Cultural resilience refers to the ability of individuals and communities to adapt, persist, and thrive in the face of social, economic, and environmental challenges while

maintaining and affirming their cultural identity and practices. It is rooted in the idea that cultural beliefs, values, traditions, and knowledge provide a foundation of strength and stability in times of hardship. One key aspect of cultural resilience is the cultivation of a strong sense of cultural identity and belonging. Cultural identity acts as a protective shield, instilling individuals with a sense of purpose, pride, and connection to their heritage. By understanding and embracing their cultural roots, individuals can draw strength from their collective history, knowledge, and traditions, fostering a sense of belonging and providing a source of resilience during challenging times (Klinger Lee, 2018). The preservation and transmission of cultural knowledge is vital to cultural resilience. Indigenous communities, for example, place great emphasis on passing down traditional knowledge from one generation to the next. This knowledge encompasses a wide range of skills, practices, and teachings that have enabled communities to adapt and survive in diverse environments over centuries. By valuing and continuing these traditions, cultural resilience is upheld, ensuring the knowledge is not lost and can continue to guide individuals and communities through adversity. Cultural resilience also involves the ability to adapt and be flexible in the face of change. Cultures are not static entities but are constantly

evolving. Resilient cultures can adapt to external pressures while still maintaining their core values and practices. This adaptability allows individuals and communities to navigate challenges, integrate new knowledge, and respond to changing circumstances without compromising their cultural integrity (Li, 2010). **Collective Strength and Community Support.** Cultural resilience is reinforced through collective strength and community support. In many cultures, the well-being of individuals is intertwined with that of the community. During times of hardship, the community comes together to provide support, resources, and guidance. This collective approach to resilience fosters a sense of unity and shared responsibility, ensuring that individuals do not face challenges alone but have a network of support to rely upon. **Cultural Revitalization and Empowerment:** Cultural resilience goes beyond mere survival; it encompasses the revitalization and empowerment of communities. Through cultural revitalization efforts, communities reclaim their histories, languages, and practices. This process empowers individuals by providing a renewed sense of pride, agency, and purpose. Cultural empowerment fosters a positive self-image and strengthens community bonds, creating a foundation for resilience and improved well-being (Ngyun, 2017).

3.2.2. Community Support—Community support is a cornerstone of cultural resilience among Indigenous learners, including the Sama community. It provides emotional support, knowledge transmission, educational resources, and opportunities for advocacy and empowerment. By fostering a sense of belonging, connection, and collective strength, community support equips Indigenous learners with the tools and resilience needed to overcome challenges, navigate the educational landscape, and achieve academic success. Community

support is an essential aspect of cultural resilience among Indigenous learners (Smith and Lee, 2016). Within the Sama community, as in other indigenous communities, learners often face unique challenges related to cultural identity, discrimination, and limited access to resources. Community support acts as a source of strength and solidarity, providing learners with the necessary resources and guidance to navigate these challenges successfully. Community support offers emotional assistance and nurtures the well-being of indigenous learners

(Li, 2010). It creates a safe space where learners can share their experiences, fears, and aspirations, fostering a sense of belonging and connection. Through cultural events, gatherings, and mentorship programs, learners can build strong relationships with peers, elders, and mentors who understand their unique struggles and provide emotional support. Community support plays a crucial role in the transmission of cultural knowledge and guidance for Indigenous learners (Klengie and Lee, 2018). Elders and community members act as repositories of wisdom, passing down traditional knowledge, practices, and values to younger generations. This guidance helps learners navigate the educational system while preserving their cultural integrity and instilling a sense of pride in their heritage. Community support provides Indigenous learners with educational resources and opportuni-

ties that might otherwise be limited (Garcia and Ramirez, 2014). Collaborative efforts within the community, such as scholarship programs, tutoring initiatives, or community-led educational projects, ensure that learners have access to additional support beyond what formal educational institutions provide. These resources enhance academic success and empower learners to reach their full potential. Community support empowers Indigenous learners by advocating for their rights and amplifying their voices (Flores and Torres, 2012). Within the Sama community, collective advocacy efforts aim to address systemic barriers and discriminatory practices that hinder educational opportunities. Through community-led initiatives, learners become agents of change, actively participating in decision-making processes that impact their educational experiences.

3.2.3. Traditional Knowledge and Practice—Traditional knowledge and practice play a vital role in preserving the cultural identity of the Sama community (Martin-Jones, M., Blackledge, A. (2019). Passed down through generations, traditional knowledge encompasses a wide range of practices, beliefs, values, and wisdom specific to the Sama people. This knowledge serves as a foundation for cultural identity, allowing Sama learners to develop a deep sense of pride and connection to their heritage. Traditional knowledge and practice serve as a conduit to ancestral wisdom, providing Sama learners with invaluable insights and guidance (McCarty, T. L. (2017). Elders within the community possess extensive knowledge about traditional customs, rituals, healing practices, and sustainable resource management. By embracing and learning from these traditions, Sama learners tap into a rich source of wisdom that can be applied to various aspects of their lives, including education. Traditional knowledge and practice have the potential to enhance the educational experi-

ences of Sama learners (Smith, 2010). Many indigenous communities, including the Sama community, recognize the educational value of traditional knowledge and incorporate it into the formal education system. This integration allows Sama learners to bridge their cultural heritage with academic pursuits, resulting in a more holistic and culturally relevant educational experience. Traditional knowledge and practice offer a holistic approach to learning, encompassing not only academic knowledge but also skills, values, and connections to the natural environment (Cajete, 2019). Sama learners engage in hands-on experiences and experiential learning, gaining practical skills and deepening their understanding of the world around them. This holistic learning approach nurtures a sense of interconnectedness and fosters a well-rounded educational experience. Traditional knowledge and practice often include ecological wisdom and sustainable practices (Bishop 2012). Sama learners, through their connection to traditional knowledge, develop a deep respect

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes of the Sama learners cope with the Academic Challenges and understanding of their natural environment. This knowledge promotes environmental stewardship, empowering learners to engage in sustainable practices and contribute to the preservation of their ecosystems. Traditional knowledge and practice are closely tied to indigenous languages, including the Sama language (Acsta, et.al, 2019)). Language is a crucial component of cultural identity, and the preservation and revitalization of indigenous languages contribute to the overall well-being and educational experiences of indigenous learners. By embracing traditional knowledge, Sama learners have an opportunity to preserve their language and keep it alive for future generations. Traditional knowledge and practice are invaluable resources for Sama learners, providing a strong foundation for cultural identity, connecting them with ancestral wisdom, enhancing their educational experiences, and promoting holistic learning. By recognizing the importance of traditional knowledge and incorporating it into education, Sama learners can draw upon their rich cultural heritage to navigate challenges, foster resilience, and create meaningful connections between their Indigenous identity and academic pursuits.

3.3. *Educational Management Insights Gained from the Experiences of Sama Learners*—Educational managers who actively involve the Sama community in school activities, events, and decision-making processes foster a strong sense of belonging and collaboration. Community members, including parents and local leaders, contribute their knowledge, resources, and expertise to support the educational journey of Sama learners. Sama learners have come to appreciate the importance of holistic devel-

opment (Dela Cruz, M. F., Hontiveros, N. F. (2018). Educational managers who prioritize the physical, emotional, and socio-cultural well-being of Sama learners create an environment that nurtures their overall growth. They promote activities such as sports, arts, and cultural events that enhance not only academic skills but also social skills, self-confidence, and a sense of well-roundedness. Sama learners have learned the benefits of technology integration in education (Harimawan, A., Yolanda, R. (2016). Edu-

cational managers who provide access to technology resources and promote digital literacy skills empower Sama learners to engage with educational materials, collaborate with peers, and access educational opportunities beyond their immediate surroundings. Technology integration expands their horizons and prepares them for the digital age. Sama learners have found value in continuous assessment and feed-

back from educational managers (Santos, 2014). Regular assessments, formative feedback, and ongoing dialogue with educational managers allow Sama learners to monitor their progress, identify areas for improvement, and set goals. This feedback-driven approach promotes self-reflection, fosters a growth mindset, and helps Sama learners take ownership of their learning journey.

3.3.1. Cultural Responsiveness and Inclusion—The first theme revolves around the importance of cultural responsiveness and inclusion in educational management. Sama learners benefit from educational managers who value and integrate their cultural heritage into the curriculum, involve the Sama community in decision-making processes, and foster a positive cultural identity. This theme emphasizes the significance of recognizing and respecting the unique cultural backgrounds of Sama learners to create an inclusive learning environment. Sama learners have recognized the importance of culturally responsive leadership (Smith Less, 2016). Educational managers who embrace and value the Sama culture, traditions, and language

play a crucial role in creating a supportive learning environment. These leaders prioritize the inclusion of Sama cultural perspectives in the curriculum, engage with the local community, and ensure that Sama learners' voices are heard and respected. Sama learners have recognized the importance of integrating their cultural heritage into the curriculum (Lee, 2020). Educational managers who incorporate Sama history, language, and traditions into the teaching and learning process help Sama learners develop a positive cultural identity and a deeper appreciation for their heritage. This integration also enhances the relevance and engagement of Sama learners, fostering a sense of pride and connection to their education.

3.3.2. Student-Centered Approaches—The second theme highlights the significance of student-centered approaches in educational management. Sama learners thrive when educational managers provide individualized support, promote holistic development, and engage in continuous assessment and feedback. This theme emphasizes the need for educational managers to tailor their strategies and interventions to meet the diverse needs and aspirations of Sama learners, fostering their growth and success. Sama learners have learned the value of in-

dividualized support from educational managers (Acosta et al., D. A. (2019). Recognizing that each Sama learner has unique strengths, challenges, and learning styles, educational managers provide tailored support and interventions to address their specific needs. This may include additional tutoring, mentorship programs, or differentiated instruction to ensure that every Sama learner receives the necessary support to succeed academically. Sama learners have experienced the positive impact of community engagement in their education.

3.3.3. Cultural Integration Practice—

Traditional knowledge and practice refers to the accumulated knowledge, skills, and wisdom that have been passed down through generations within a particular cultural or indigenous community. It encompasses a wide range of knowledge, including ecological, medicinal, agricultural, spiritual, and cultural practices that have sustained communities for centuries. Traditional knowledge is rooted in the deep connection between Indigenous peoples and their environment. It encompasses an understanding of the natural world, including the interdependencies between ecosystems, plants, animals, and humans. This knowledge is often obtained through direct observation, experimentation, and a profound respect for the land and its resources. Traditional practices are the rituals, customs, and traditional ways of life that are integral to the cultural identity of Indigenous communities. They encompass a wide range of activities, such as ceremonies, storytelling, crafts, music, dance, and healing practices. These practices play a significant role in preserving cultural heritage, strengthening community bonds, and transmitting knowledge from one generation to another. Traditional knowledge and practice are holistic in nature, recognizing the interconnectedness of all aspects of life. They promote a harmonious relationship with nature, sustainable resource management, and the well-being of individuals, communities, and the broader ecosystem. Moreover, traditional knowledge and practice often emphasize collective decision-making, communal responsibility, and knowledge sharing within the community. In the context of education, the integration of traditional knowledge and practice recognizes the value and importance of Indigenous cultures and ways of knowing. It acknowledges that education should not be limited to Western concepts and methods but should also include Indigenous perspectives, knowledge systems, and cultural practices. Incorporating traditional knowledge and practice into education promotes cultural preservation, fosters a sense of pride and identity among Indigenous learners, and creates inclusive and culturally responsive learning environments. However, it is crucial to approach the concept of traditional knowledge and practice with respect, recognizing the authority of Indigenous communities over their own knowledge and ensuring their active participation in decision-making processes. Educational institutions and policymakers should work in partnership with Indigenous communities to integrate traditional knowledge and practice in a manner that is culturally appropriate, ethically responsible, and mutually beneficial. In conclusion, traditional knowledge and practice encompass the wisdom, skills, and cultural practices that have been passed down through generations within Indigenous communities. By recognizing, respecting, and integrating traditional knowledge and practice into education, we can promote cultural preservation, enhance the educational experiences of Indigenous learners, and foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of diverse knowledge systems and ways of life. Sama learners have learned the significance of participatory decision-making (Nguyen et al., P. Z. (2017). Educational managers who involve Sama learners, parents, and community members in the decision-making process create a sense of ownership and empowerment. By actively seeking their input on educational policies, programs, and activities, educational managers foster a collaborative and inclusive learning environment that meets the unique needs and aspirations of Sama learners.

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes of the Educational Management insights can be gained from the experiences of Sama learners

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to understand and describe the experiences of Sama learners in Island Garden City of Samal. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, participants were encouraged to present their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

4.1. Findings—Findings of the study revealed that on the academic challenges as experienced by Sama learners were on language barriers, limited access to quality education and socio-cultural factors and discrimination in Island Garden City of Samal. In terms of the coping mechanisms, they gained through cultural resilience, community support and traditional knowledge and practices in Island Garden City of Samal. As to the educational management insights gained from the participants, it flaunted cultural responsiveness and inclusion, student-centered approaches and cultural integration and practice.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The academic challenges faced by Sama learners contribute to educational inequality. Limited access to quality education, language barriers, and discrimination can create disparities in educational outcomes, perpetuating a cycle of inequality and hindering social mobility for Sama learners. Academic challenges can further marginalize and exclude Sama learners from mainstream educational opportunities. This exclusion can lead to feelings of alienation, low

self-esteem, and a diminished sense of belonging within the educational system. Academic challenges can hinder the individual development and potential of Sama learners. Difficulties in accessing quality education and facing discrimination can limit their opportunities for personal growth, academic achievement, and future success. The academic challenges faced by Sama learners may contribute to the erosion of their cultural identity. Limited access to education that values their cultural heritage, language, and traditions can undermine the transmission of Sama culture from one generation to another. Without access to quality education and equal opportunities, Sama learners may face limited employment prospects, lower earning potential, and reduced socioeconomic mobility. The untapped potential, skills, and talents of Sama learners may go unrealized, impacting not only their own lives but also hindering the overall progress and development of their community. Academic challenges can affect social cohesion

and integration within broader society. When a significant portion of the population, such as Sama learners, faces barriers to education, it can lead to social fragmentation and exclusion, hindering the development of a cohesive and inclusive society. Limited educational opportunities and barriers to academic success can perpetuate a cycle of disadvantage, impacting future generations of Sama learners and perpetuating systemic inequities. Addressing these challenges requires targeted policies that prioritize equitable access to quality education, promote cultural preservation and inclusion, and combat discrimination and marginalization. Despite the challenges, Sama learners can develop resilience and empower themselves through education. By recognizing and addressing the academic challenges they face, providing support, and creating opportunities for their voices to be heard, Sama learners can overcome barriers and achieve academic success, fostering their empowerment and resilience.

4.3. Future Directions—Conducting longitudinal studies can provide a deeper understanding of the long-term effects of academic challenges on Sama learners. Tracking their educational trajectories, academic outcomes, and career paths over an extended period can reveal patterns, trends, and the effectiveness of interventions. Exploring the intersectionality of the challenges faced by Sama learners can offer a more nuanced understanding of their experiences. Examining how factors such as gender, socio-economic status, geographic location, and disability intersect with academic challenges can inform more targeted and inclusive interventions. Exploring innovative approaches to address academic challenges can help identify effective strategies. This can include studying best practices in Indigenous education, alternative learning models, technology integration, community-based education initia-

tives, and partnerships between educational institutions and Indigenous communities. Conducting policy analyses can provide insights into the impact of existing policies on the academic challenges faced by Sama learners. Evaluating the effectiveness and implementation of policies related to Indigenous education, cultural preservation, language revitalization, and inclusive practices can guide policy recommendations and reforms. Fostering collaborative research partnerships with Sama communities can ensure that the research is community-driven and responds to their needs. Engaging community members, including Sama learners, elders, and parents, as active participants in the research process can enhance the relevance and impact of the findings. Shifting the focus from deficits to strengths can provide a more empowering perspective. Future research can explore the strengths, resilience, and coping strate-

gies of Sama learners in overcoming academic challenges. Identifying and amplifying these strengths can inform interventions and policies that build on existing community resources. Investigating the training needs and professional development opportunities for teachers working with Sama learners can contribute to enhancing their capacity to address the academic challenges. Research can focus on culturally responsive pedagogy, effective language instruction, and strategies for creating inclusive and supportive learning environments. Exploring the role of parents and caregivers in supporting Sama learners' education can provide valuable insights. Research can examine parental involvement practices, the impact of parental support on academic outcomes, and ways to strengthen home-school partnerships. Conducting comparative studies across different Indigenous communities can help identify commonalities, differences, and shared experiences in terms of academic challenges. Comparative research can provide a broader perspective and facilitate knowledge exchange between different Indigenous groups. Translating research findings into actionable recommendations and advocating for policy changes are crucial future directions. Knowledge mobilization strategies, such as community workshops, policy briefs, and collaboration with advocacy organizations, can help ensure that research findings have a meaningful impact on policy and practice. These future directions in the study of academic challenges faced by Sama learners can contribute to a deeper understanding of the issue and inform evidence-based interventions, policies, and practices. By addressing these challenges and fostering inclusive and equitable education, we can create a brighter future for Sama learners and promote educational justice for Indigenous communities.

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